

Research Protocol

For the paper entitled: Overcoming Challenges in Agile and DevOps Integration: A Qualitative Study

Submitted to the Lean and Agile Software Development Track
ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing 2026

Authors: Author 1, Author 2, Author 3, Author 4

26.09.2025

Contents

1	Introduction	4
2	Research Goal	4
3	Data Collection	4
3.1	Development of the interview guide	4
3.2	Sample and participants information	5
3.3	Conducting the interviews	5
4	Data Analysis	6
4.1	Deductive Coding	6
4.2	Inductive Coding	6
4.3	Consolidation	6
4.4	Synthesis of Findings (Code-Matrix Overview)	8
A	Interview Guide	10
B	Code Overview	12
C	Code Hierarchy Models	13
D	Code Matrices	14
E	Codebook	15

List of Figures

1	Example of the coding and clustering process	7
2	Consolidated Code Hierarchy - Challenges	7
3	Consolidated Code Hierarchy - Solutions	8
4	MAXQDA Code Overview	12
5	MAXQDA Code Hierarchy Model - Challenges	13
6	MAXQDA Code Hierarchy Model - Solutions	13
7	MAXQDA Code Matrix - Challenges	14
8	MAXQDA Code Matrix - Solutions	14

List of Tables

1 Participants Demographics 5

1 Introduction

This protocol details a qualitative study of the organizational challenges involved in the integration of Agile and DevOps and the solutions used to address them. It delineates the research questions, study design, purposive sampling, instruments, data collection, analysis procedures, and measures to enhance validity.

The study draws on semi-structured interviews with six experienced industry professionals in Brazil and Germany, each with extensive experience in both domains. The resulting data are analyzed using qualitative content analysis following Mayring’s methodology [1, 2] to identify patterns, themes, and important findings. By specifying these elements in detail, the protocol ensures transparency and reproducibility so that other researchers can replicate or extend the study.

2 Research Goal

To focus the inquiry and guide subsequent data collection and analysis, the study is organized around two research questions (RQ):

- **RQ1:** What challenges do practitioners face when integrating Agile methodologies with DevOps practices?
- **RQ2:** What strategies and tools have proven effective in addressing these Agile-DevOps integration challenges in professional software development settings?

3 Data Collection

To address the research questions, we collected primary data through semi-structured interviews. This approach allowed for comparable coverage of key topics while preserving openness to participant narratives. The interview guide was developed and piloted prior to fieldwork, a prospective sample of experienced practitioners was recruited, and interviews were conducted one-to-one via Zoom video conferencing, recorded with consent, and transcribed verbatim.

3.1 Development of the interview guide

An interview guide (see Appendix A) was created to enable structured but open-ended conversations. First, a broad pool of potential questions and topics was compiled based on the study goals. The items were then reviewed to ensure they were open-ended, comprehensible, and non-leading. The remaining prompts were then ordered to establish a clear progression and grouped into higher-level thematic blocks for coherence. In addition, questions were classified as either a *fixed core* or an *optional probe*. The fixed open-ended core questions were posed to all participants to ensure consistent coverage, while optional follow-ups were used at the discretion of the interviewer to clarify points, deepen details on specific issues, or prompt further elaboration as needed. To ensure that the interview guide was optimal and to have an idea of how long an interview would take, a pilot interview was conducted with a participant outside the study sample. Minor refinements were made before the guide was used in the study.

Interview guide. The finalized guide (Appendix A) comprised a brief ethics preamble followed by three sections aligned with the study goals:

- **Preliminaries and ethics:** confirmation of consent to record; assurance that recordings would not be shared; anonymity; and agreement that results may be published.
- **Section 1 — Introduction and background:** organization type; industry context; current role and tenure; total years of professional experience; self-assessed familiarity with Agile and DevOps using 0–10 scales; and years working in Agile and DevOps environments.

- **Section 2 — Identifying challenges (RQ1):** how DevOps was introduced (timing, triggers, and whether adoption was top-down or team-led) and principal challenges encountered when integrating Agile and DevOps; optional probes targeted organizational structure influences and technical/process frictions, including (when feasible) a ranking of the most limiting obstacles.
- **Section 3 — Strategies and tools (RQ2):** practitioner advice and concrete strategies; compatibility of Agile methods with DevOps; collaboration across previously siloed roles; practices and tools supporting integration; balancing quality with speed; useful metrics; forward-looking trends; and a final open prompt for additional insights.

Across sections, the interviewer followed the fixed items to secure consistent coverage, using optional probes as needed to clarify points, deepen detail on salient issues, or prompt further elaboration while preserving the participant’s narrative flow.

3.2 Sample and participants information

The sample comprised six experienced industry professionals selected via purposive sampling to ensure relevance to Agile–DevOps integration. Inclusion criteria were:

- At least five years of total experience in software development or related roles;
- Practical experience with both Agile methodologies and DevOps practices;
- Direct involvement in Agile–DevOps integration efforts in real projects.

Participants contributed diverse perspectives across organizational contexts and roles. All had over ten years of experience overall, including 9–20 years with Agile and 5–20 years with DevOps. Two participants were based in Brazil and four in Germany, providing cross-cultural insights (see Table 1).

Participant	Country/ Language	Company Type	Role	Total Exp.*	Agile Exp.*	DevOps Exp.*
P1	Germany/English	Freelancer	Agile Coach	24	17	15
P2	Brazil/Portuguese	Tech Company	Engineering Director	24	20	20
P3	Germany/English	IT Consulting Company	Consultant/ Product Owner	20	13	10
P4	Brazil/Portuguese	State-owned Public Company	Developer/ Architect	20	11	11
P5	Germany/English	IT Consulting Company	Managing Director (Dev/Arc/DevOps)	30	15	9
P6	Germany/English	IT Consulting Company	Consulting Director/ Team Lead	10	9	5

Table 1: Participants Demographics

3.3 Conducting the interviews

Six one-to-one interviews were conducted via Zoom between 21.05.2025 and 16.06.2025, each lasting between 30 and 50 minutes. Interviews were conducted in English (n=4) or Portuguese (n=2; see Table 1). With informed consent, all sessions were recorded and transcribed verbatim. For the two Portuguese interviews, analyses used the original Portuguese transcripts to preserve meaning and tone. Only quoted excerpts were translated into English by the first author (a native Portuguese speaker fluent in English).

Interviews followed the established guide in the specified sequence. Within each section, participants were encouraged to speak freely without interruption to preserve the integrity of their narratives. Prompts and follow-up questions were adapted to the conversational flow, with predefined probes used when additional detail or clarification was needed. Each interview concluded with an invitation for the participant to add any desired information to the discussion.

4 Data Analysis

To prepare the qualitative dataset, each interview was transcribed using one of three tools: MAXQDA Transcription [3], Zoom’s automatic transcription [4], or Descript [5]. Each tool was chosen based on availability. All transcripts were manually reviewed and corrected by the first author to resolve automatic transcription errors and omissions and ensure verbatim accuracy. These verified transcripts formed the corpus for a qualitative content analysis following Mayring [1, 2], combining deductive and inductive coding phases. This approach provides a transparent and structured procedure for systematically interpreting and evaluating qualitative material. Coding and data management were conducted in MAXQDA, and its integrated AI assistance was used to surface potentially overlooked codes; all AI-suggested candidates were inspected and incorporated only when warranted by the data.

4.1 Deductive Coding

In the first step, a set of deductive codes was developed based on the research questions and the findings from the literature review on Agile-DevOps integration. These included, for example:

- **Challenges:** Cultural Barriers; Cross-Functional Misalignment; Knowledge and Experience Gaps; Tooling Issues; Communication Gaps.
- **Strategies:** Cross-Functional Teams; Integrated Responsibility; Adaptive Practices; Automation Tools; Proactive Monitoring.

Each transcript was coded against this scheme. While the deductive pass ensured direct coverage of the research focus, several segments remained uncoded, motivating a complementary inductive phase.

4.2 Inductive Coding

The second phase aimed to capture themes that emerged directly from the participants’ responses and were not represented in the previous code scheme. Coding units were defined as full responses to individual questions. Following Mayring’s paraphrasing–abstraction steps, statements were condensed and generalized into new codes. Where appropriate, existing codes were reused and their definitions refined.

Recording units were defined as full responses to individual questions. Following Mayring’s paraphrasing–abstraction steps [1, 2], statements were condensed and generalized into new codes, where appropriate existing codes were reused and their definitions refined. To illustrate this procedure, Figure 1 shows how verbatim excerpts were paraphrased/abstracted into codes and then grouped into a higher-order category. Newly identified codes were added to the codebook and then applied across transcripts in a follow-up pass to ensure complete and consistent coverage.

4.3 Consolidation

The results of the deductive and inductive coding phases were integrated through a systematic consolidation process. After coding all interviews, provisional codes were inspected for overlaps and potential groupings, then merged or renamed to form a coherent code system. Code definitions were refined accordingly (see Codebook in Appendix E). Each transcript was then re-read using the consolidated code list (see Appendix B) to ensure complete and consistent application, with adjustments made where warranted. Using comparative synthesis across cases, we identified recurring patterns and thematic convergences as well as notable outliers, and organized related themes under higher-order categories. The resulting hierarchy is visualized in Figure 2 (Challenges) and Figure 3 (Solutions). The hierarchy visualization was also made possible within the MAXQDA Software as shown in Appendix C.

On the challenges side (see Figure 2), codes describing misconceptions about Agile/DevOps (e.g., treating Agile as a rigid recipe or “tool-first” adoption of DevOps) were combined as **C1.1 Cultural Barriers & Misconceptions**. Notes on resistance to change, bureaucratic routines, and entrenched processes were reconciled into **C1.2 Organizational Inertia**. Items capturing handoff friction, unclear ownership across development/operations/security, and silo boundaries were merged as **C1.3 Cross-Functional Misalignment**. Dependence on vendors or external security/infra teams was grouped as **C2.1 Dependency on**

Figure 1: Example of the coding and clustering process

Figure 2: Consolidated Code Hierarchy - Challenges

Figure 3: Consolidated Code Hierarchy - Solutions

External Providers, while observations about growth and specialization creating coordination overhead were consolidated as **C2.2 Increasing Team Size/Specialization**. Trade-offs between feature throughput, quality, and operational duties were harmonized under **C3.1 Balancing Priorities**. Concerns about ceremony overhead and heavyweight frameworks were categorized as **C3.2 Inefficiency/Complexity of Agile**. Signals of weak traceability and patchy monitoring were integrated into **C4.1 Lack of End-to-End Observability**.

For solutions (see Figure 3), practices advocating durable, cross-disciplinary teams (including infra and security) were consolidated as **S1.1 Cross-Functional Teams**. Statements emphasizing joint ownership of build, deploy, and run activities (including on-call) formed **S1.2 Integrated Responsibility**, and empowerment to deploy/rollback without manual, centralized approval gates, was grouped as **S1.3 Decentralized Autonomy**. The Scrum Master’s unblocking role (e.g., removing external dependencies) yielded **S1.4 Scrum Master’s Role**. Measures promoting open information flow and shared visibility were integrated as **S2.1 Transparency & Openness**, while alignment of rewards with collaborative outcomes informed **S2.2 Incentive System**. Change tactics (pilot teams, internal champions, targeted training) were reconciled as **S3.1 Change Management Strategies**, context-sensitive method tailoring (e.g., Kanban/Scrumban, reducing ceremony) as **S3.2 Adaptive Practices**, and staged roll-out as **S3.3 Gradual Expansion**. Finally, themes around instrumentation and metrics were merged as **S4.1 Proactive Monitoring**, cadence and progressive rollout practices as **S4.2 Controlled Release Approach**, and CI/CD, testing, and infra automation under **S4.3 Automation Tools**.

4.4 Synthesis of Findings (Code-Matrix Overview)

Following the content analysis and consolidation of the code hierarchy, we conducted a cross-case synthesis to integrate results across interviews, develop a coherent account of the findings, and support the formulation of conclusions. To assess topic prominence, we used MAXQDA’s Code-Matrix Browser (see Appendix D) to examine both *breadth* (number of participants mentioning a category) and *intensity* (number of coded segments per participant). On the challenges side, **C1 Cultural & Organizational Barriers** showed the broadest coverage, as it was discussed by five of six participants with multiple segments each, whereas **C4 Technical Limitations** appeared in only one interview. **C2 Structural Constraints** and **C3 Process & Method Complexity** showed moderate coverage (appearing in a subset of interviews). On the solutions side, **S1 Team Structure & Autonomy** and **S3 Process & Change Management** were widely discussed (five of six participants), while **S4 Automation & Infrastructure** and **S2 Culture & Collaboration** appeared in fewer interviews (two each), though with concentrated depth in specific cases (e.g., high segment counts for **S4** in P2 and P4). We use these matrices descriptively, as a qualitative indicator of topic prominence, rather than as statistical evidence. Lower-frequency topics may still be consequential in context.

References

- [1] Philipp Mayring. Qualitative content analysis. *Forum Qualitative Sozialforschung / Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 1(2), Jun 2000. doi: 10.17169/fqs-1.2.1089. URL <https://www.qualitative-research.net/index.php/fqs/article/view/1089>.
- [2] Philipp Mayring and Thomas Fenzl. *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse*, pages 691–706. Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, Wiesbaden, Germany, 2022. doi: 10.1007/978-3-658-37985-8_43. URL https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-37985-8_43.
- [3] VERBI Software GmbH. Maxqda transcription, 2025. URL <https://www.maxqda.com/automatic-transcription>. Software.
- [4] Zoom Video Communications, Inc. Using audio transcription for cloud recordings, 2025. URL https://support.zoom.com/hc/en/article?id=zm_kb&sysparm_article=KB0064927.
- [5] Descript, Inc. Transcription, 2025. URL <https://www.descript.com/transcription>.

A Interview Guide

Interview Guide: Overcoming Challenges in Agile and DevOps Integration

Interview Guide: Overcoming Challenges in Agile and DevOps Integration

- Brief personal introduction.
- Goal of the project.

Preliminary Questions

1. Would it be alright if I record this interview?
 - *Recordings won't be published or shared.*
2. The results of this study will be published as part of a scientific paper at the University of Emden/Leer. There's also a chance it may be shared in other academic or professional forums. Would that be OK with you?
 - *Responses remain anonymous.*

Section 01: Introduction

1. Which company or type of organization do you currently work for?
2. Which industry or industries do you primarily work in?
3. What is your current role or job title? Can you briefly describe your responsibilities and how long you've been in this role?
4. How many years of total professional experience do you have in software development, IT operations, or related fields?
5. On a scale from 0 to 10, how would you rate your personal knowledge or experience with Agile practices?
(0 = no experience, 10 = highly experienced and confident with Agile in practice)
6. How many years have you worked in environments that actively applied Agile methodologies?
7. On a scale from 0 to 10, how would you rate your personal knowledge or experience with DevOps practices?
(0 = no experience, 10 = highly experienced and confident in applying DevOps)
8. How many years have you worked in environments where DevOps practices were actively implemented?

Section 02: Identifying challenges

1. Can you provide a brief overview of how DevOps has been introduced or integrated into your current work environment?
For example, when did it begin? What triggered the shift? Was it top-down or team-lead?
2. What are the biggest challenges that you have faced when integrating Agile and DevOps practices?
3. *Optional: In your experience, how have traditional organizational structures influenced the integration of Agile and DevOps?*
4. *Optional: What technical or process-related challenges have you encountered when trying to merge Agile's iterative development with DevOps' continuous delivery model?*
5. *Optional: Of all the mentioned challenges, which do you think are the most significant or limiting – and why? (if possible, could you rank them in terms of impact?)*

Section 03: Discussing strategies

1. Based on your experience, what advice would you give to others on how to effectively address the previously mentioned challenges?
2. *Optional: Which Agile methodology have you found most compatible with DevOps practices and why?*
3. *Optional: What strategies have you found effective for fostering collaboration between traditionally siloed roles, such as development, operations, and management?*
4. *Optional: What strategies have you employed to maintain quality while increasing delivery speed?*
5. *Optional: Are there any practices or tools that you recommend to support Agile-DevOps integration?*
6. What metrics have you found most useful for measuring the success or progress of Agile-DevOps integration?
7. In your opinion, what does the future of Agile-DevOps integration look like? Are there any emerging technologies or practices that you believe will shape it further?
8. Is there something else you would like to share that we haven't covered, but you feel is important for the understanding of Agile and DevOps integration?

B Code Overview

The screenshot displays the MAXQDA Code Overview interface. It shows a hierarchical tree of codes with a total count of 92. The tree is organized into several main categories: Challenges, Solutions, and Metrics. Each category is further divided into sub-categories and individual codes, with counts provided for each level. The interface includes expand/collapse icons (chevrons) and a search icon (magnifying glass) for each code.

Code	Count
Codes	92
Challenges	0
Cultural & Organizational Barriers	0
Cultural Barriers & Misconceptions	15
Organizational Inertia	5
Cross-Functional Misalignment	4
Knowledge & Experience Gaps	3
Structural Constraints	0
Dependency on External Providers	2
Increasing Team Size/ Specialization	1
Remote Work Challenges	1
Process & Method Complexity	0
Balancing Priorities	2
Inefficiency/Complexity of Agile Methods	2
Technical Limitations	0
Lack of End-to-End Observability	1
Solutions	0
Team Structure & Autonomy	0
Cross-Functional Teams	5
Integrated Responsibility	4
Decentralized Autonomy	5
Scrum Master's Role	1
Culture & Collaboration	0
Transparency and Openness	3
Incentive System	1
Process & Change Management	0
Change Management Strategies	4
Adaptive Practices	6
Incremental Deployment	1
Gradual Expansion	1
Automation & Infrastructure	0
Proactive Monitoring	2
Controlled Release Approach	2
Automation Tools	5
Metrics	16
Sets	0

Figure 4: MAXQDA Code Overview

C Code Hierarchy Models

Figure 5: MAXQDA Code Hierarchy Model - Challenges

Figure 6: MAXQDA Code Hierarchy Model - Solutions

D Code Matrices

Figure 7: MAXQDA Code Matrix - Challenges

Figure 8: MAXQDA Code Matrix - Solutions

E Codebook

Codebook

Challenges & Solutions to Agile-DevOps Integration

28.07.25

Code System

1 Challenges	0
1.1 Cultural & Organizational Barriers	0
1.1.1 Cultural Barriers & Misconceptions	15
1.1.2 Organizational Inertia	5
1.1.3 Cross-Functional Misalignment	4
1.1.4 Knowledge & Experience Gaps	3
1.2 Structural Constraints	0
1.2.1 Dependency on External Providers	2
1.2.2 Increasing Team Size/ Specialization	1
1.2.3 Remote Work Challenges	1
1.3 Process & Method Complexity	0
1.3.1 Balancing Priorities	2
1.3.2 Inefficiency/Complexity of Agile Methods	2
1.4 Technical Limitations	0
1.4.1 Lack of End-to-End Observability	1
2 Solutions	0
2.1 Team Structure & Autonomy	0
2.1.1 Cross-Functional Teams	5
2.1.2 Integrated Responsibility	4
2.1.3 Decentralized Autonomy	5
2.1.4 Scrum Master's Role	1
2.2 Culture & Collaboration	0
2.2.1 Transparency and Openness	3
2.2.2 Incentive System	1
2.3 Process & Change Management	0
2.3.1 Change Management Strategies	4
2.3.2 Adaptive Practices	6
2.3.3 Incremental Deployment	1
2.3.4 Gradual Expansion	1
2.4 Automation & Infrastructure	0
2.4.1 Proactive Monitoring	2

2.4.2 Controlled Release Approach	2
2.4.3 Automation Tools	5
3 Metrics	0
3.1 Recovery Time	2
3.2 Delivery Speed	2
3.3 Employee Satisfaction	1
3.4 Customer Value	1
3.5 Customer Satisfaction	2
3.6 Incident Frequency	3
3.7 Deployment Frequency	4
3.8 Deployment Optimization	1

1 Challenges

What challenges do practitioners face when integrating Agile methodologies with DevOps practices?

1.1 Challenges >> Cultural & Organizational Barriers

This cluster addresses the **deeply embedded values, beliefs, and power structures** that prevent Agile and DevOps practices from taking root. These barriers are **systemic and attitudinal**, often more difficult to change than tools or processes. They are a major source of **pseudo-agile implementations** or failed transformations.

1.1.1 Challenges >> Cultural & Organizational Barriers >> Cultural Barriers & Misconceptions

This code captures **misunderstandings, resistance, or superficial adoption** of Agile and DevOps practices due to **deep-rooted cultural issues**. Includes **over-reliance on tools or frameworks** without adopting their underlying principles or without the necessary cultural or process changes.

1.1.2 Challenges >> Cultural & Organizational Barriers >> Organizational Inertia

Resistance to change due to established structures, legacy systems, or historical success.

1.1.3 Challenges >> Cultural & Organizational Barriers >> Cross-Functional Misalignment

Disconnects between key teams (e.g., Dev & Ops) due to structural separation, conflicting priorities, siloed workflows or mindset. Reflects a lack of shared understanding, empathy, or communication between specialized roles. Leads to friction during handovers, deployment, or collaboration.

1.1.4 Challenges >> Cultural & Organizational Barriers >> Knowledge & Experience Gaps

Lack of practical experience or cross-functional knowledge among team members, particularly when developers lack operational expertise or when infrastructure specialists lack coding skills.

1.2 Challenges >> Structural Constraints

This cluster focuses on **external or internal organizational structures** that create friction or limit agility. These are often **practical or logistical barriers** that limit how Agile and DevOps principles can be applied in practice.

1.2.1 Challenges >> Structural Constraints >> Dependency on External Providers

Challenges resulting from relying on third-party infrastructure or services.

Ex: a challenge that is explicitly tied to a vendor, external system, or contractual limit.

1.2.2 Challenges >> Structural Constraints >> Increasing Team Size/ Specialization

Communication and coordination problems due to increasing team size and specialization.

1.2.3 Challenges >> Structural Constraints >> Remote Work Challenges

Difficulties in communication and collaboration due to remote work.

1.3 Challenges >> Process & Method Complexity

This category captures challenges arising from the **design, rigidity, or ambiguity** of delivery methods and workflows. These challenges often lead to **confusion, frustration, or misuse of agile methods**, especially when teams are expected to follow prescribed rituals without adaptation to context.

1.3.1 Challenges >> Process & Method Complexity >> Balancing Priorities

This code refers to the **challenges of managing conflicting demands** within Agile/DevOps teams, such as striking a balance between day-to-day operations and development goals, or balancing the need for speed and the need for error avoidance.

1.3.2 Challenges >> Process & Method Complexity >> Inefficiency/Complexity of Agile Methods

Critique of the ineffectiveness or overcomplexity of certain Agile methodologies or frameworks in certain contexts.

1.4 Challenges >> Technical Limitations

This category includes **infrastructural or system-level weaknesses** that prevent effective implementation of Agile or DevOps. These technical issues may seem minor, but they often block **automation, feedback loops, and reliability**, which are core to DevOps.

1.4.1 Challenges >> Technical Limitations >> Lack of End-to-End Observability

Monitoring and troubleshooting complex distributed systems.

2 Solutions

What strategies and/or tools have proven effective in addressing the challenges in Agile & DevOps integration?

2.1 Solutions >> Team Structure & Autonomy

This category captures solutions related to how teams are **structured, composed, and empowered** to function in Agile-DevOps environments. It includes practices that **redistribute responsibility, promote autonomy, and break down traditional role silos**.

2.1.1 Solutions >> Team Structure & Autonomy >> Cross-Functional Teams

Team structure changes with role mix. Teams including Dev, Ops, QA, etc.

2.1.2 Solutions >> Team Structure & Autonomy >> Integrated Responsibility

Refers to teams taking full responsibility for developing, running and supporting their own systems. Referred to as "you build it, you run it".

Ex: when devs are responsible for live operations or downstream reliability.

2.1.3 Solutions >> Team Structure & Autonomy >> Decentralized Autonomy

Refers to the **delegation of authority and decision-making** to individual teams or contributors, allowing them to act independently without requiring top-down approval.

Ex: Teams making choices on architecture, process, or prioritization; **Shared or distributed leadership models**, where leadership roles are rotated, collaborative, or situational.

2.1.4 Solutions >> Team Structure & Autonomy >> Scrum Master's Role

Importance of the Scrum Master in resolving impediments.

2.2 Solutions >> Culture & Collaboration

This category includes solutions that target the human and social dynamics essential for Agile-DevOps success. It covers the cultural mindset, motivational structures, and communication patterns that foster transparency, trust, and shared responsibility.

Unlike technical or structural changes, these enablers are often intangible but deeply influential. They help teams break down silos, encourage constructive collaboration, and align individual behavior with collective goals.

2.2.1 Solutions >> Culture & Collaboration >> Transparency and Openness

Embracing transparency and not hiding issues or problems.

2.2.2 Solutions >> Culture & Collaboration >> Incentive System

The role of rewards and incentives in shaping organizational behavior.

2.3 Solutions >> Process & Change Management

This category brings together strategies aimed at **adapting processes**, managing transitions, and handling complexity in Agile-DevOps environments. These solutions reflect how organizations **introduce, scale, and tailor** agile and DevOps practices over time.

2.3.1 Solutions >> Process & Change Management >> Change Management Strategies

The importance of a balanced, top-down and bottom-up approach to implementing organizational change.

2.3.2 Solutions >> Process & Change Management >> Adaptive Practices

Refers to the intentional adjustment of practices, tools, or frameworks based on the specific context of a project, team, or organization.

2.3.3 Solutions >> Process & Change Management >> Incremental Deployment

Implementing changes in small, controlled increments to limit risk.

2.3.4 Solutions >> Process & Change Management >> Gradual Expansion

Proposing the idea of gradually expanding successful practices to other parts of the organization.

2.4 Solutions >> Automation & Infrastructure

This category covers solutions that provide the **technical automation and procedural scaffolding** necessary to support Agile and DevOps practices. It reflects how organizations use tooling and structured release mechanisms to ensure **reliable, repeatable, and safe delivery** of software.

2.4.1 Solutions >> Automation & Infrastructure >> Proactive Monitoring

Developing robust monitoring systems to detect issues quickly. Involves alerting systems, logs, dashboards.

2.4.2 Solutions >> Automation & Infrastructure >> Controlled Release Approach

A delivery strategy that emphasizes structured, time-based releases over continuous deployment. It typically involves cutoff dates, batching of changes, scheduled deployments, and pre-release testing to reduce risk and ensure quality.

Note: this approach contrasts with continuous integration and delivery, favoring a predictable cadence (e.g., weekly or biweekly) and centralized control over when changes are pushed to production. It is especially useful in regulated, complex, or risk-sensitive environments.

2.4.3 Solutions >> Automation & Infrastructure >> Automation Tools

Any tool or script to automate. Ex: CI/CD, monitoring, testing, IaC (Infrastructure as Code), etc.

3 Metrics

3.1 Metrics >> Recovery Time

The duration required to regain or restore a previous state.

3.2 Metrics >> Delivery Speed

The speed at which the team delivers features or tasks.

3.3 Metrics >> Employee Satisfaction

Perception of team members' emotional state and enthusiasm in the work environment.

3.4 Metrics >> Customer Value

Perceived benefits received by customers in relation to the cost.

3.5 Metrics >> Customer Satisfaction

Measure of how products and services meet or exceed customer expectations.

3.6 Metrics >> Incident Frequency

A control metric, indicating the impact of self-inflicted errors.

3.7 Metrics >> Deployment Frequency

A proxy for agility, indicating the pace of change.

3.8 Metrics >> Deployment Optimization

Strategies for reducing the time and complexity of deployments.